

Investigation of Some Bioactivities and Isolation of L-Dopa Compound from *Mucuna prurines* (L.) DC. (Khwele-Ya) Seed

Aye Myint Sein^{*}, Htet Htet Aung^{**}, Khin Cho Lwin^{***}

Abstract

Mucuna Prurines (L.) DC. (Khwele-ya) seed was chosen for screening of the physicochemical properties and some pharmacological actions. Moreover, bioactive organic compound (L-Dopa) was isolated from the seed of *M. Prurines*. The present study deals with the investigation of elemental analysis, nutritional values, antimicrobial activity and antioxidant activity. Some nutrient elements as well as some toxic elements in seed of *M. Prurines* were carried out by EDXRF method and AAS methods. According to EDXRF method and AAS methods, K was the most abundant element and toxic elements were found to be absent. Nutritional values such as moisture content (11.40%), ash content (5.64%), fat content (6.87%), carbohydrate content (33.29%) and fibre content (36.00%) of seed were found to be determined by using the respective method. In antimicrobial screening, H₂O, EtOH, EtOAc and PE extracts for seed sample was examined by using agar disc diffusion method. In the DPPH staining, the methanol extract of *M. Prurines* seed had the highest radical scavenging activity, since it showed from minimum value of 6.25µg to 400 µg. Isolation of major amino acid compound from *M. Prurines* (Khwele-ya) seed was also carried out.

Keywords: *Mucuna Prurines* (L.) DC. Antimicrobial activity, Antioxidant activity

Introduction

Mucuna genus is found all over the world in the woodlands of tropical areas especially in tropical Africa, India and the Caribbean. This genus belongs to the family Fabaceae. It is also found in Asia, America and Africa. *M. pruriens* is a tropical legume, commonly known as velvet bean or cowitch or cowhage. It is one of the most popular medicinal plants in Africa and Asia, and is constituent of more than 200 indigenous drug formulations. The demand for mucuna in India as well as in international drug markets increased many fold only after the discovery of the presence of L-3, 4-Dihydroxyl Phenyl Alanine (L-DOPA), an anti-Parkinson's (PD) disease drug in the mucuna seeds (Eze, C. N, 2017). All parts of *M. prurita* possess valuable medicinal properties. The seeds are traditionally used for astringent, laxative, aphrodisiac, analgesic and Parkinson's diseases. The leaves are applied to ulcers. The roots are used for nervous disorders, blood purifier and diuretics (Kavitha C. and C. Thangamani, 2014).

Materials and Methods

M. prurines (khwele-ya) seed was collected from Thu Htay Kone Village, Maubin township, in December 2018. The collected samples were identified by authorized botanists, in Department of Botany, Maubin University. Samples were air-dried for two to three weeks. The dried samples were made into powder by using blender and then stored in air-tight container.

Elemental Analysis of Plant Sample by EDXRF

The element contents of *M. prurines* seed powder was determined by EDXRF (Shimadzu EDX-7000); C-H balance method. In order to determine the heavy toxic

^{*} Dr., Associate Professor, Department of Chemistry, Bago University

^{**} Demonstrator, Department of Chemistry, Maubin University

^{***} MSc candidate

metals and macronutrient elements in *Mucuna prurines* was determined by EDXRF method (Griken et al., 1986) at Department of Physics, Maubin University.

Elemental Analysis of *Mucuna Prurines* Seed by Atomic Absorption Spectrophotometry

The sample was weighed and then pre-ashing was carried out on a hot plate until all the combustible materials were burnt. Pre-ash sample was placed inside the electric muffle furnace and heated gradually raising temperature until 450°C. The process of heating, cooling and weighing were repeated, until constant weight of ash sample was obtained. 0.5 g of dried sample was placed into a porcelain crucible. 5 mL of HNO₃: HCl (1:4) concentrated acid mixture was also added it. The solution was evaporated to dryness overnight on a hot plate. Leach the residue on a sample was mixed with 10 mL of HNO₃ acid mixture at a temperature of about 70°C for 30 minutes. The solution was stirred by using vortex mixer. The solution was filtered and aspirated on an atomic absorption spectrophotometer (AA-7000 Series Model AAS) at Department Chemistry, Maubin University.

Determination of Nutritional Values of *Mucuna Prurines* Seed

The nutritional value of the dried powder sample was determined by AOAC methods for moisture, ash, protein, crude fiber and crude fat and carbohydrate.

Screening of Antimicrobial Activity

The specimens will be cultured in Department of Botany, University of Yangon. Nutrient agar was prepared according to the method described by Cruickshank, 1975. For the examination of *in vitro* antimicrobial activity, solvent extracts such as PE, EtOAc, EtOH, and H₂O extracts of the sample from *M. prurines* were investigated by using agar disc diffusion method.

Rapid Screening of Antioxidant by Dot-Blot and DPPH Staining

DPPH (1,1-diphenyl-2-picryl-hydrazyl) radical scavenging assay was chosen to assess the antioxidant activity of plant materials. Each diluted sample of the methanol extracts was carefully loaded onto a 6 cm × 6 cm TLC layer (silica gel GF₂₅₄ precoated plates; Merck) and allowed to dry (3 min). Drops of each sample were loaded, in order of decreasing concentration (400, 200, 100, 50, 25, 12.5, 6.25 and 3.125 µg/mL), along the row (Chang, H.Y., *et al.*. (2007). The sheet bearing the dry spots was placed upside down for 10 s in a 60 µM DPPH solution. The intensity of the yellow color depends upon the amount and nature of radical scavenger present in the sample (Huang et al., 2004).

Isolation of L-Dopa from the *Mucuna prurines* (Khwele-ya) Seed

The dried milled seeds (100 g) were defatted with acetone (300 ml) by shaking for 48 h at RT and defatted material was extracted with water-ethanol (1:1) with 0.1% ascorbic acid (3 × 500 ml) by shaking overnight. The residue was removed by filtration and filtrates were pooled and concentrated. The concentrate after crystallization yielded crude L-DOPA, which on further recrystallization in hot water gave pure crystals (Misra, L.*et al.*, 2007). Compound-1 (2.9%) was isolated from *M. prurines* seed. Isolated compounds from *M. prurines* was checked under 254 and 365 nm light and classified with the colour reaction tests.

Results and Discussion

Elemental Analysis of Plant Sample by EDXRF

Some nutrient elements as well as some toxic elements in seed of *M. prurines* were carried out by EDXRF method (Shimadzu EDX-8000). In accord with EDXRF spectral results, K (1.11%), P (0.38%), Ca (0.07%), S (0.21%), Fe (0.02%) and Cu (0.01%) in *M. prurines* seed. Among them, potassium was the most predominant in *M. prurines*.

Figure1. EDXRF spectrum of *Mucuna prurines* (Khwele-ya) seed

Elemental Analysis of *Mucuna Prurines* Seed by Atomic Absorption Spectrophotometry

Quantitative determination of the elements in *M. prurines* seed sample was carried out by AAS as shown in Table 1. From this table it was found out that, K was more predominant than other elements in samples. K has the highest content 17.93mg/ kg in seed.

Table 1. The Concentration of some Metal in Seed of *Mucuna Prurines* (Khwele-ya) by AAS Method

Element	Metal Content (mg/ kg)
K	17.93
Ca	11.23
Mg	0.33

Determination of Nutritional Values of *Mucuna Prurines* Seed

The determination of ash, fat, fiber, moisture and protein content were made according to AOAC method. Nutritional values such as moisture content (11.40%), ash content (5.64%), fat content (6.87%), protein content (6.80%), fibre content (36.00%) and carbohydrate content (33.29%) of seed were found to be determined by using the respective method. As a result, it was found that fibres were present as major nutrient in samples.

Screening of Antimicrobial Activity

In antimicrobial activity of the different crude extracts were screened by using agar disc diffusion method. PE, EtOH, EtOAc and H₂O extracts of *M. prurines* seed showed antimicrobial activity against *Bacillus subtilis*, *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Pseudomonas fluorescens*, *Aspergilla flavous*, *Candida albicans* and *Escherichia coli* species. H₂O, EtOH and EtOAc extracts showed high activity (zone of inhibition ranged from 8 to 16mm). PE extract also showed moderate activity against *Aspergilla flavous* (ID 10 mm).

Figure 2. Antimicrobial screening of crude extracts from *Mucuna Prurines* (khwele-ya) seed

Rapid Screening of Antioxidant by Dot-Blot and DPPH Staining

To make a semi-quantitative visualization possible, methanol extracts from *M. prurita* seed were detected in the TLC plates by DPPH staining method. For the rapid screening each different amount samples was applied as a dot (d, 1 cm) on a TLC plate. Dots from left to right (3.125 μ g to 400 μ g). That was then stained with DPPH solution as shown in Figure 3. (Change et al., 2007). In the DPPH staining, the methanol extract of *M. prurita* seed had the highest radical scavenging activity, since it showed from minimum value of 6.25 μ g to 400 μ g.

Figure 3. Screening of antioxidant activity of *Mucuna Prurines* (Khwele-ya) seed

Identification of Isolated Compound from *Mucuna Prurines* (L.) DC. (Khwele-ya) Seed

Amino acid compound, white amorphous was isolated from the seed of *M. prurines*. Its R_f value is 0.85, silica gel GF₂₅₄ precoated TLC plate with solvent system: acetone: chloroform: acetic acid: n-butanol: water (6:4:4:4:3) ratio. It gave a dark violet colour in UV (254 and 365 nm) light. It gave also violet spot on TLC plate with ninhydrin reagent indicating the presence of the amino acid. In UV-vis spectrum in water (Figure 4 (a), Table 2), the maximum absorptions were 231 and 282 nm. Absorption peak at 231nm represents the C = C chromophore with the excitation energy $\pi \rightarrow \pi^*$ transition while the peak at 282 nm is related to C = O chromophore with excitation energy $n \rightarrow \pi^*$ transition. The maximum absorption bands at 231nm and 282 nm were found to be very similar with those of amino acid skeleton. UV-vis spectral data of compound are identical with that of reference compound L-Dopa. In FT IR spectrum (Figure 5) the absorption at 3346 cm^{-1} was due to phenolic OH stretching, 2925 cm^{-1} and 2854 cm^{-1} were for C-H stretching $-\text{CH}_3$, $-\text{CH}_2$ groups, 1618 cm^{-1} indicated the stretching band of $>\text{C} = \text{O}$ group, 1510 cm^{-1} suggested the in plane bending vibration of N-H groups, 1377 cm^{-1} showed $-\text{C}-\text{N}$ stretching vibration, asymmetric and symmetric stretching in aromatic C-O-C at 1275 and 1077 cm^{-1} . These UV and FT IR spectral data also support isolated compound may be L-DOPA.

Figure 4. (a) UV spectrum of isolated compound
(b) UV spectrum of standard L-DOPA

Figure 5. FT IR spectrum of isolated compound

Table 2. UV Spectral Data of Isolated Compounds Compare with Standard L-DOPA

Sample	Solvent used	λ_{max} (nm) observed	Remarks
compound	water	231, 282	π to π^* transition
L-DOPA	water	236, 283	of C=C chromophore & n to π^* transition of C=O chromophore

Conclusion

As the biological screenings, antimicrobial activities and DPPH staining were demonstrated and biological active compound (L-Dopa) were isolated from activity guided plant extracts.

The elemental analysis was carried out by EDXRF and AAS method. According to EDXRF method, it was found that potassium peak was also the most predominant and heavy toxic elements were not detected. In accord with EDXRF spectral results, K (1.11%), P (0.38%), S (0.21%), Ca (0.07%), Fe (0.02%) and Cu (0.01%) in *M. prurines* seed. K has the highest content (1.11%) in seed. However, some toxic elements, Cd and Pb were not observed in this sample. By AAS method, it was found that potassium was the most abundant element and toxic elements were found to be absent in the seed. From this study, K has the highest content 17.93mg/kg in seed. Nutritional values such as moisture content (11.40%), ash content (5.64%), fat content (6.87%), protein content (6.80%), fibre content (36.00%) and carbohydrate content (33.29%) of seed were found to be determined by using the respective method. As a result, it was found that fibres were present as major nutrient in seed sample. The different crude extracts (H₂O, EtOH, EtOAc and PE) of *M. prurines* seed showed antimicrobial activity against *Bacillus subtilis*, *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Pseudomonas fluorescens*, *Aspergilla flavous*, *Candida albicans* and *Escherichia coli* species. Seed extracts also showed antimicrobial activity against these six pathogenic strains (zone of inhibition ranged from 8 to 16 mm). Major amino acid compound (2.9%) we isolated from *M. prurines* seed. Isolated compound was identified by TLC, UV and FT IR. This Isolated compound was compared with standard L-Dopa. In the DPPH staining, the methanol extract of *M. prurines* seed had the highest radical scavenging activity, since it showed from minimum value of 6.25µg to 400 µg. Therefore, main constituent of *M. prurines* (khwele-ya) seed may contribute significantly to potent antioxidant activity.

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